

Possible Anti-Parkinsonian Compounds. Part II. Synthesis of Acetyl 3,5-Dihalo-Salicyloylamines, Piperazines and Phenotheiazines

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Acetyl 3 : 5 dihalo salicyloyl chlorides have been condensed with simple secondary-amines¹, 1-aryl-piperazines² and phenothiazine³ with a view to test their anti-Parkinsonian activity.

ACETYL-salicylic acid is itself a central nervous system depressant¹. Since Parkinsonism is caused mainly by the excess involuntary movements², it was thought desirable to prepare different condensation products of acetyl 3 : 5 dihalo-salicyloyl chlorides with simple secondary amines, 1-aryl-piperazines and phenothiazine. Amines like simple secondary amines, 1-aryl piperazines and phenothiazines, form the basic moiety of most of the anti-Parkinsonian drugs³⁻¹².

Pharmacology

The observation that most of the anti-cholinergic drugs are also potent anti-Parkinsonian agents¹³, led the authors to screen the synthesized compounds for their anti-cholinergic activity. For anti-cholinergic activity atropine sulphate was selected as standard. The ratio between the test samples and the standard was measured. The compounds were tested by the Magnus guinea-pig ileum screen but none of the compounds was found to be superior to atropine-sulphate and with much lower-activity of the order of 1/1000 of atropine.

Experimental

1-Aryl piperazines were synthesised by the mixed hydrochlorides of aromatic primary amines and diethanolamine¹⁴.

3 : 5-dichloro and 3 : 5-dibromo salicylic acids were acetylated with acetic anhydride and a few drops of conc. sulphuric acid to give acetyl 3 : 5 dichloro and 3 : 5 dibromo salicylic acids.

Acetyl 3 : 5-dichloro/dibromo salicyloyl chloride :

A mixture of acetyl-3 : 5-dihalo-salicylic acid (0.1 M) and thionyl chloride (0.12 M) was shaken at room temperature for 1 hr. and then refluxed for 4 hr on a steam-bath, subsequently, after distilling

off the excess of thionyl chloride under reduced pressure and cooling the mixture, the residue was crystallised from dry benzene.

Acetyl 3 : 5-dihalo (3 : 5-dichloro and 3 : 5 dibromo) salicyloyl dimethylamine :

Dimethylamine (0.1 M) in dry benzene was taken in a flask and then a mixture of acetyl 3 : 5 dihalo-salicyloyl chloride (0.1 M) and potassium carbonate (0.15 M) was added to it. The contents of the flask were refluxed under anhydrous conditions for 2 hr. The inorganic materials were filtered off and dry benzene was removed by distillation under reduced pressure. On trituration of the viscous product with petroleum ether (40-60%), a solid mass was obtained which was washed with sodium-bicarbonate solution and then with water to remove any unreacted acid and recrystallised from methanol or acetone.

Acetyl 3 : 5 dihalo(3 : 5-dichloro/3 : 4-dibromo) salicyloyl amines, 1-aryl-piperazines and phenothiazine :

To a solution of acetyl-3 : 5 dihalo salicyloyl chloride in dry carbon tetrachloride, potassium carbonate (0.15 M) and simple secondary amines (0.1 M) or phenothiazine (0.1 M) or 1-aryl piperazines (0.1 M) in dry-carbon-tetrachloride was added and the mixture was stirred for half an hour at room temperature. After refluxing the above mixture for 6 hr on a steam-bath under anhydrous conditions and cooling, the mixture was filtered. Subsequently on removing carbon tetrachloride by distillation, the solid mass, which was obtained, was recrystallised from a suitable solvent after washing with sodium bicarbonate solution and then with water.

Various compounds thus prepared are listed in Table 1.

TABLE I. ACETYL 3:5 DICHLORO/3:5 DIBROMO SALICYLOYL AMINES, PHENOTHIAZINE AND PIPERAZINES

Comp. No.	X	R	M.P. °C	Molecular Formula	Analysis					
					Carbon Calcd.	Carbon Found	Hydrogen Calcd.	Hydrogen Found	Nitrogen Calcd.	Nitrogen Found
1.	Br	Dimethylamino (a)	105	C ₁₁ H ₁₁ NO ₃ Br ₂	36.16	36.52	3.01	3.25	3.83	3.45
2.	Br	Diethylamino (b)	140	C ₁₃ H ₁₅ NO ₃ Br ₂	36.69	39.42	3.81	3.54	3.56	3.25
3.	Br	Morpholino(c)	115	C ₁₃ H ₁₃ NO ₄ Br ₂	38.32	38.54	3.19	3.49	3.43	3.41
4.	Br	Piperidino(b)	90	C ₁₄ H ₁₅ NO ₃ Br ₂	41.48	41.69	3.70	3.52	3.45	3.30
5.	Br	Pyrrolidino(c)	125	C ₁₃ H ₁₃ NO ₃ Br ₂	39.63	38.58	3.32	3.44	3.58	3.71
6.	Br	Diphenylamino(b)	160	C ₂₁ H ₁₅ NO ₃ Br ₂	52.06	52.40	3.09	3.14	2.86	2.65
7.	Br	Diethanolamino(c)	100-1	C ₁₃ H ₁₅ NO ₅ Br ₂	36.70	36.98	3.50	3.29	3.29	3.11
8.	Cl	Diethylamino(d)	98	C ₁₃ H ₁₅ NO ₃ Cl ₂	51.15	51.65	4.95	4.65	4.62	4.52
9.	Cl	Morpholino(c)	95	C ₁₃ H ₁₃ NO ₄ Cl ₂	49.21	49.50	4.10	4.37	4.41	4.31
10.	Cl	Pyrrolidino(b)	115	C ₁₃ H ₁₃ NO ₃ Cl ₂	51.82	51.55	4.31	4.55	4.65	4.89
11.	Cl	Piperidino(d)	105	C ₁₄ H ₁₆ NO ₃ Cl ₂	53.33	53.65	4.76	4.55	4.49	4.34
12.	Cl	Diphenylamino(c)	130	C ₂₁ H ₁₅ NO ₃ Cl ₂	63.15	63.65	3.78	3.55	3.50	3.25
13.	Cl	Diethynolamino(d)	95	C ₁₃ H ₁₅ NO ₃ Cl ₂	43.58	43.95	4.47	4.65	4.17	4.34
14.	Cl	Dimethylamino(e)	100-2	C ₁₃ H ₁₁ NO ₃ Cl ₂	48.70	49.15	4.00	3.95	5.09	5.24
15.	Cl	Phenothiazino(e)	140	C ₂₁ H ₁₃ NO ₃ SCl ₂	63.15	63.85	3.25	3.42	3.50	3.66
16.	Br	Phenothiazino(c)	145	C ₂₁ H ₁₃ NO ₃ SBr ₂	48.55	48.94	2.50	2.10	2.69	2.88
17.	Cl	1-phenyl-piperazino(b)	125	C ₁₉ H ₁₈ N ₂ O ₃ Cl ₂	58.16	58.55	4.59	4.88	7.14	7.43
18.	Cl	p-tolyl-piperazino(e)	115	C ₂₀ H ₂₀ N ₂ O ₃ Cl ₂	59.11	59.69	4.92	4.82	6.89	6.42
19.	Cl	o-tolyl-piperazino(a)	120	C ₂₀ H ₂₀ N ₂ O ₃ Cl ₂	59.11	59.54	4.92	4.68	6.68	6.66
20.	Cl	m-tolyl-piperazino(e)	116	C ₂₀ H ₂₀ N ₂ O ₃ Cl ₂	59.11	59.66	4.92	4.54	6.89	6.44
21.	Br	1-phenyl-piperazino(c)	130	C ₁₉ H ₁₈ N ₂ O ₃ Br ₂	47.30	43.89	3.73	3.41	5.69	5.23
22.	Br	p-tolyl-piperazino(e)	128	C ₂₀ H ₂₀ N ₂ O ₃ Br ₂	48.38	48.14	4.03	4.53	5.69	5.23
23.	Br	o-tolyl-piperazino(b)	120	C ₂₀ H ₂₀ N ₂ O ₃ Br ₂	48.38	48.69	4.03	4.29	5.64	5.88
24.	Br	m-tolyl-piperazino(d)	120	C ₂₀ H ₂₀ N ₂ O ₃ Br ₂	48.38	48.78	4.03	4.34	5.64	5.79
25.	Br	1-phenyl-2'-methyl piperazino(a)	90	C ₂₀ H ₂₀ N ₂ O ₃ Br ₂	48.38	48.89	4.03	4.64	5.64	5.86

Notes: (i) All the melting points are uncorrected.

(ii) The percent yield ranged from 50-65.

(iii) Recrystallised from:

a = Methanol-acetone; b = ethanol; c = ethanol-benzene; d = benzene and e = methanol.

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